
PROCEDURE FOR STATE REGISTRY OF RIGHTS TO BUILDINGS AND CONSTRUCTIONS

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Abstract.

State registration procedure and information of buildings and structures, registration procedure based on legal documents after completion of a building or structure on land plots allocated according to the established procedure, according to the appropriate procedure for state registration registration and database creation.

Keywords.

Right to registration, register, database, above-ground - underground, buildings, operational management.

Property rights to buildings and structures located on the ground, above the ground and underground, the right to manage the economy and the right to operational management. should be carried out.

The right of a certain legal entity or individual to buildings and structures located on a separate plot of land and having a separate cadastral number, including auxiliary buildings next to them, is an object of registration. Rights to various auxiliary buildings are not registered separately from the main building or structure. State registration of ownership rights to apartments and non-residential premises in multi-apartment buildings is carried out separately for each owner.

The rights to housing belonging to housing construction companies are registered in the name of the relevant company, with the list of members of this

company attached. The rights to buildings and structures whose construction is completed and accepted for use in the prescribed manner are transferred from the state register.

In the event that buildings and structures owned by legal entities and individuals are included in the charter fund of newly created legal entities, the property rights to these buildings and structures are registered in the name of newly created legal entities. Original copies of documents must be submitted for state registration of rights to real estate. Documents confirming the establishment of property rights to buildings and structures are as follows:

The decision of the mayor of the city (district) to approve the act of the commission on accepting the completed building, structure, house into use; approved by notary offices, sale, gift, exchange, inheritance, lease, contracts and transfer-acceptance of enterprises based on this, acts of privatization of state property, and decisions issued by the court. State registration of the right to buildings and structures is carried out if there are relevant documents confirming this right. During the state registration of the right to buildings and structures, the organization that registers: performs on-site inspection of the application and legal documents attached to it, their legality, concluded agreements, the condition of buildings and structures, cadastral collection Having studied the volume, the number of participants in joint ownership rights, if relevant documents are available, studying their shares, there is an application for the state registration of these buildings and structures from other persons. or not, compares the rights to real estate and the transactions concluded on it with the state register. The rights to buildings and structures owned by several legal entities and individuals in joint property rights are registered in the names of the owners in the shares specified in the documents establishing the right. If the participants of shared property rights have determined by mutual agreement the procedure for using individual parts of the common building and structure (rooms, apartments, etc.) in accordance with their shares, and this agreement is notarized, then such an agreement should be registered at their request. Rights to buildings and structures, property rights to them, in cases where the documents determining the right are presented by the family members or heirs of the owners who have been declared missing or dead by the court according to the documents, it is registered in the order of inheritance.

State registration of property rights to buildings and structures and other material rights, rights to real estate and agreements concluded on it, the relevant rights of certain legal and natural persons to these objects in the state register,

restrictions, cancellation of rights, rights to real estate and agreements concluded about it, and by creating a computer database and reporting on the state of state cadastre objects of buildings and structures and their use, submits to the unified system of state cadastres in the prescribed manner.

Summary: If we do not change our relationship with the earth, we cannot use it effectively. Because today, land neglect, salinization and corrosion are blindly allowed. Therefore, since the land is our national wealth and an important basis of our prosperous life, it is time to make changes to our laws regarding its rational use. If today we neglect our holy land like mother, we will neglect ourselves, if we forget every inch of land on which our navel blood dripped, we will forget ourselves. Today, if we understand the reforms and ask ourselves questions, if we are able to properly use the resources of the earth, the future generation will be proud of us.

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